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A Study of Literary Festivals in Ireland from a Management Perspective

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Further Reading:

McGuckin, M., Linehan, M. &
Leahy, R. (2025) Narratives and
Networks: Managing Ireland's
Literary Festivals, Event
Management, 29(4), 585-600.
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Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Literary festivals are important drivers of literary tourism, connecting readers, authors and cultural stakeholders while supporting regional cultural development. Despite their significance, they remain underexplored within festival and event management research, which has largely focused on audience dynamics rather than organisational practices. This study addresses that gap by examining literary festivals in Ireland through a management lens, with attention to governance, planning, business models and marketing. Using qualitative and quantitative methods, it aims to understand how these festivals evolve and operate, and how management practices influence their sustainability, cultural value and contribution to tourism and destination development.

Research Findings

The study identifies key components required for effective literary festival management, highlighting the importance of balancing artistic vision, operational delivery, financial sustainability, and community engagement. Successful festivals demonstrate strong strategic planning, expert programming, and innovative festivalscape design. They also require robust governance structures that enhance transparency and accountability, along with diversified funding models to ensure financial resilience. Innovative communication approaches and immersive audience engagement strategies help festivals broaden their reach and improve attendee experience. Together, these findings provide a clearer understanding of how Irish literary festivals function within the wider cultural and tourism ecosystem.

Policy Implications

Literary festivals contribute significantly to cultural development, tourism, and regional identity, but their long-term sustainability depends on targeted policy support. Policymakers should prioritise multi-annual funding structures, capacity-building initiatives and professional development pathways that recognise festivals' evolving organisational needs. Strengthening partnerships between local authorities, arts agencies, tourism bodies and festival organisers would enhance resource sharing and regional impact. Policies that support volunteer development, cultural programming and destination marketing can further strengthen festival resilience. Understanding festivals' economic, cultural, and social benefits provides a compelling rationale for ongoing investment to ensure these events continue enriching communities and supporting Ireland's cultural landscape.

Industry Recommendations

Festival organisers should adopt structured management frameworks that support sustainable operations, financial resilience and strong community relationships. A typology of festival models, a collaborative business framework and a stakeholder engagement model can guide organisers in refining governance, revenue diversification and volunteer coordination. The study's integrated ten-step management framework provides a practical blueprint for planning, delivering, and marketing festivals effectively. By implementing these approaches, organisers can improve decision-making, strengthen accountability, enhance cultural programming and increase audience engagement. These strategies support resilience, long-term viability, and meaningful cultural and tourism impacts within Ireland's festival landscape.

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